

ABUSIVE SUPERVISION AND ORGANIZATIONAL CYNICISM AS PREDICTORS OF CYBER-LOAFING AMONG FEDERAL CIVIL SERVICE EMPLOYEES IN ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

This study examined abusive supervision and organizational cynicism as predictors of cyber-loafing among federal civil service employees in Anambra State, Nigeria. Three hundred and twenty-nine (329) public sector employees served as participants in the study. The participants were 147 males and 182 females. The age of the participants ranged from 27 to 53 years, with a mean age of 39yrs and standard deviation of 1.42yrs. The participants were selected through cluster and simple random sampling technique. Being a cross-sectional survey studies, correlation design and multiple regression analysis were used as the appropriate design and statistical tool to analyze the data obtained from the field study respectively. The result confirmed that abusive supervision significantly predicted cyber-loafing among federal civil servants in Nigeria at $\alpha = .51$, $p < .05$ ($n=229$). Also organizational cynicism significantly predicted cyber-loafing among federal civil servants at $\alpha = .63$, $p < .05$ ($n=229$). It is recommended that organizational leader-member exchange be improved to checkmate abusive supervision while increasing fairness and equity in the organization.

Keywords: abusive supervision, waste management workers, organizational cynicism, counterproductive workplace behaviour

1. Introduction

The presence of computers and internet in organization has created more problematic situation with stories of abuse and workers hiding under its usage to short-change their

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organizations (Pearson, 2013; Young, 2010). This sort of problem is what many authors regarded as cyber-loafing. Despite its productive use, computers and the internet are becoming a growing concern in the workplace because of the distraction they bring in the workplace through social media networking, emailing, game plays, music and video sharing (Lim & Chen, 2012, Coker, 2013).

Cyber-loafing, also known as cyber-slacking refers to employees' use of Internet and e-mail services provided by their employer for non-work purposes during working hours. In other words, it is a high-tech method for employees to shirk their job duties while appearing to be working (Messarra, Karkoulian & McCarthy, 2011). Cyber-loafing may include e-mailing jokes to friends, online shopping or game playing, downloading music, instant messaging, posting to newsgroups, or surfing non-work-related Internet sites (Coker, 2013). Although other forms of loafing have become counterproductive in the work setting, the problem associated with cyber-loafing or internet surfing is more dangerous because of its appeal across all ages and culture. As bad as the behaviour is to the organization, scholars are becoming aware that cyber-loafing being a work-deviant behaviour may be a form of retaliatory behaviour. Consequently, focus of this study is ascertained whether abusive supervision and organizational cynicism are antecedents to cyber-loafing.

Theoretically, all forms of abuse preempt retaliation directly or indirectly and it can be exhibited in the short term or long term. There is a belief given the antecedents of Nigerian work setting, that cyber-loafing are indirect effects of abusive supervision which is hostile actions of superiors toward their subordinates in the workplace (Mary, 2012) and also superior's inordinate behaviour towards his/her subordinates in a way that affects their jobs or their persons. There is connection that employees look for means for compensating for their abuse in the workplace and this may be found in taking advantage of organizational resources for personal purposes e.g. using the computer and internet services for emails, audio and video sharing etc.

Another antecedent to this cyber-loafing behaviour is organizational cynicism which is negative perceptions about the organization and its system born out of distrust and loss of faith against the organization, management or persons in the organization (Dean, Brandes & Dharwadkar, 1998). Ikechukwu-Ifudui and Myers (2015) using employees in the Nigerian banking sector as a case study confirmed that lack of trust and abuse is the leading cause of cynicism at work which also correlates with the present study.

2. Statement of the Problem

The danger of converting organizational resources to personal usage such as: the internet facilities, computer and other electronic gadgets is more and more of a problem in the workplace than ever (Beugre, & Kim, 2006; Zoghbi-Manrique-de-Lara, 2012; Ugrin, & Pearson, 2013). This is because the attitude poses great danger to job, employee and organizational outcomes in most significant ways. There is also the

problem of disrupting normal organizational productivity as most workers who are victims of cyber-loafing expend greater number of hours avoiding work in order to surf or loaf on the internet without executing officially the duties of their workplace. In the instances of the above, workplace cyber-loafing may be reactions to negative organizational outcomes (Young, 2010) and may also affect the personality of the employees in more significant ways such as; cynical behaviours.

There is a growing concern that poor human interaction in the workplace as being experienced by many organizations in the wake of the advent of computer and the internet is robbing the workplace intrigues of human dynamics essential for socialization process in the workplace which is important for organizational effectiveness. The instances of the above represent a problematic situation for the employees and the organization in general as they affect productivity and efficiency.

Undetected cyber-loafing comes at a great financial cost to organizational as several downloads, Wifi audio and video sharing through unauthorized organizational medium increase organizational running cost. Most of these are tapped into by the employees or hacked into for external persons in connection and collaboration with an employee which may be harmful to the organization.

There is the danger of radicalization of the organizational members as cyber-loafing opens a window of unregulated interaction between a member of one organization and another at the expense of exposing organizational secrets and revealing classified information of the organization to people who may be injurious to the organization goals. Hence, there is this concern that high scale organizational sabotage leading to an eventual terrorism may emanate from cyber-loafing.

It is also worrisome that crime wave among employees is on the increase with little or no remediation and may be wired through cyber-loafing. Employees may in collaboration with questionable element hack into the organizational vault for selfish unauthorized purposes at a great cost to the organization.

2. Literature

2.1 Cyber-loafing

Cyber-loafing is an important issue facing organizations as more employers are providing employees with computer, Internet and e-mail access at work. There are a wide range of factors that could affect with its prevalence in the workplace such as: sabotaging organizational efforts, poor inter-personal relationship among workers and between employees and their supervisors, learned workplace incivility, unproductivity, counterproductive workplace behaviour, organizational deviance behaviour, turnover intentions and actual turnovers (Young, 2010; Liberman, Seidman, McKenna & Buffardi, 2011; Wagner, Barnes, Lim, & Ferris, 2012). These negative antecedents which emanate from cyber-loafing come at a huge cost to the organization with dire consequences which may threaten organizational existence (Lim & Chen, 2012; Coker, 2013. Without proper examination of organizational factors which may lead to more

workers engaging in the behaviour, there may be no clue on how to curb the menace. This study has therefore proposed that the relationship between superiors and their subordinates such as abusive supervision and employee cynicism may be likely factors that fuel the prevalence of cyber-loafing in the workplace.

2.2 Abusive Supervision

Abusive supervision describes the hostile actions of managers toward their subordinates (Mary, 2012). Abusive supervision is also superior's inordinate behaviour toward his/her subordinates in a way that affects their jobs or their persons. Abusive supervision includes looking down on workers, ignoring their requests, withholding vital information that could aid their performance, downgrading their performance and maligning their ability. When subordinates are abused by their supervisors, they look to coworkers for support and behavioural guidance and may lose their respect for their superiors at work. If they see that deviant behaviours like theft and shirking are accepted, they are more likely to engage in those behaviours themselves for respite or restitution (Mary, 2012). Kelly and Benneth (2002) asserted that the past decade has recorded an explosion of interest and research on the topic of abusive supervision. Such behaviours typically include ridiculing and humiliating subordinates in public, refusing to speak with subordinates, or otherwise debasing subordinates. Research suggests that abusive supervision has a detrimental effect on a number of job outcomes.

Abusive supervision leads to counterproductive work behaviour (Tapper, 2000). If a subordinate encountered abusive supervision as a result of being late to work is a typical example of how abusive supervision could lead to counterproductive work behaviour. He or she may decide to form the habit of lateness as revenge to abusive supervision, saying after all, he or she will only be abused and that is all. Though "abuse" may conjure images of physical violence it is not included in the activities encompassed by the term – actions such as belittling, undermining, or yelling at subordinates are classic examples of abusive supervision. It should come as no surprise that victims of abusive supervision are likely to commit acts of organizational deviance – things like theft, sabotage, and the shirking of duties. Increasing such people have been found to be cyber-loafers, withdrawn and keeping to themselves or pretending to be occupied with work while they actually do no work other than surf the internet!

2.3 Organizational Cynicism

General cynicism is an inborn and determined personality trait which reflects generally negative perceptions about human behavior. Organizational cynicism is an individual's negative feelings, such as: anger, disappointment, hopelessness, about many problems both for the staff and organizations (Ozler & Atalay, 2011). Organizational cynicism is the negative attitudes of an individual in connection with his/her organization (Kalağan, 2009). Cynicism can be expressed both overtly, such as through direct statements questioning the integrity of the organization, and covertly through the use of sarcastic humor and nonverbal behaviors, such as "knowing I looks," "rolling eyes,"

and “smirks” (Dean, Brandes, & Dharwadkar, 1998). Cynicism is negative and is therefore a sensitive topic to managers and organizations. Because of this sensitivity, negative attitudes as well as the organizational practices that foster them have been relatively neglected in management research (Nair & Kamalanabhan, 2010). Cynics may feel embarrassment, hatred and even dishonor when they think about their organizations and have doubts about their fulfillment of their careers within their organizations. Cynicism is also defensive response, because it can shield employees against feeling strong emotions and prepare them for the next “inevitable failure” (Abraham, 2000) and can lead to other organizational counterproductive and deviant behaviours such as cyber-loafing.

Cynical behaviours emanate from unfavourable organizational climate leading to negative perceptions of the workplace, the management and organization. Other problematic situations such as: direct and indirect retaliatory behaviours on persons and resources of the organization e.g. cyber-loafing disrupt installed production capacities and effectiveness of an organization and actually accrue from varying negative feeling and perceptions about the organization. Cynicism or cynical behaviour in the workplace is also an evaluative judgment that stems from an individual’s employment experiences. Irrespective of the accuracy or validity of the individual’s perceptions on which the employee’s cynicism construct is based, it is real in its consequences (Bruch, & Vogel, 2006).

Cynical employees may be withdrawn due to lack of trust and may likely be consumed by the presence of the computer or the internet as an escape route. Organizations with a history of cynical behaviour indirectly promote individualism which leads to a wide range of organizational negative behaviours. Individualistic lifestyles are known to facilitate withdrawal behaviour or anti-social behaviours which makes more employees vulnerable to cyber-loafing. It is in view of the dangers which cyber-loafing cause to the organization such as lowered productivity, ineffectiveness and inefficiency that the search for its antecedents became the interest of this study.

2.4 Research Question

In consideration of the behavioral antecedents in Nigerian organizations and reviewed literature, pertinent questions arise. They are:

1. Will abusive supervision significantly predict cyber-loafing among public sector employees?
2. Will organizational cynicism significantly predict cyber-loafing among public sector employees?

2.5 Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this study is to examine if abusive supervision and organizational cynicism will significantly predict cyber-loafing among public sector employees. Specifically, the objectives of this study are to determine if:

1. Abusive supervision will significantly predict cyber-loafing among public sector employees.
2. Organizational cynicism will significantly predict cyber-loafing among public sector employees.

2.6 Relevance of the Study

Cyber-loafing comes at a huge cost to the organization ranging from loss of man hours to lowered productivity. Finding out how organizations will reduce the menace is of critical importance to organizational success and relevance. The study is designed to identify predictors of cyber-loafing in the organization is timely and relevant.

There is also the importance of letting organizations cultivate the habit of supervising and monitoring idle employees in the workplace because they are the most vulnerable group to cyber-loafing. The relevance of monitoring this group of idle employees is to find out the kind of information that those employees are sourcing, people they may be communicating with and information they are disseminating within the cyber world. This kind of evaluation and supervision is a positive step towards curbing the ugly trends of cyber-loafing and reducing the negative effects.

The importance of this study will also enable organizations to ensure a good interactive atmosphere within the organization, one that is devoid of rancor, acrimonious associations and divisiveness which are one of the reason employees are withdrawn leading to inactivity and cyber-loafing in the organization. To forestall employee sabotage there is need to reduce individualism among organizational members which will reduce cyber-loafing. With improved relationship among organizational members, trust will be restored and cyber-loafing will be minimized.

3. Method

3.1 Participants

Three hundred and twenty-nine (329) public sector employees served as participants in the study. The study participants were drawn from employees of Federal Civil Service in Anambra state. The participants were 147 males and 182 females. The age of the participants ranged from 27 to 53 years, with a mean age of 39yrs and standard deviation of 1.42yrs. The participants were selected through cluster and simple random sampling technique. Simple random sampling was used to select the participants across six (6) ministries, departments and agencies (MDAs).

3.2 Instrument

The study made use of three instruments for the data collection namely; cyber-loafing questionnaire by Li and Chung (2006), Abusive supervision scale by Tepper (2000) and Organizational cynicism is developed by Dean, Brandes, and Dharwadkar (1998).

3.3 Cyber-Loafing Questionnaire

Cyber-loafing questionnaire is a 24-item questionnaire developed by Li and Chung (2006). The author reported an internal consistency of .77 for the general cyber-loafing scale and .85 and .68 for activity and behaviour subscales. Sample items include: "I use the Internet during work for private purposes to extend my social network", "I use the Internet during work for private purposes to search information", "I use the Internet during work for private purposes to play a game online", "I use the Internet during work for private purposes to buy goods". Each of the four activities is represented by three items on a five-point scale ranging from (1) "(Almost) Never" to (5) "(Almost) Always". This scale consisted of three items per behaviour on a five-point scale ranging from (1) "(Almost) Never" to (5) "(Almost) Always". For its use in this study, a pilot study was carried out to ascertain its reliability and the result of the Cronbach's alpha coefficient confirmed that the instrument is reliable at .79.

3.4 Abusive supervision

Abusive supervision scale is a 15-item scale designed by Tepper (2000) to measure abusive supervision as perceived by subordinates. Participants will be required to respond to each item on a 5-point Likert scale indicating the extent to which they agree or disagree with each of the statements made in the questionnaire ranging from 1=strongly disagree to 5= strongly agree. For instance: 1=Strongly Disagree (SD), 2=Disagree (D), 3=Undecided (U), 4=Agree (A), 5 = Strongly Agree (SA) (Tapper, 2000). Tapper (2000) reported reliability index for the Scale as .95. For its use in this study, a pilot study was carried out to ascertain its reliability and the result of the Cronbach's alpha coefficient confirmed that the instrument is reliable at .68.

3.5 Organizational cynicism

Organizational cynicism is measured using a scale developed by Dean, Brandes, and Dharwadkar (1998). It is a 14-item scale designed by the authors to measure cynical behaviours of the employees regarding their organizations. The authors obtained a coefficient alpha .94 for the scale. This measure consists of fourteen items and utilized a five-point response format with strongly disagree (1) and strongly agree (5) as endpoints. Sample items include: "I believe my organization says one thing and does another", "I often experience anxiety when I think about my organization" and "I complain about how things happen in my organization to friends outside the organization. For the validity and reliability of the scale; although the scale have been validated by the original authors who obtained .94 internal consistence of the scale, for its use in this study, the reliability was enhanced during the pilot study using 50 participants from Anambra State civil service. Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient analysis was accepted at .75 for the scale.

3.6 Procedure

3.6.1 Pilot Study

The study started with a pilot study to ensure the instruments for the study are reliable measures of the constructs. Consequently, responses of 50 participants who are civil servants from Anambra State civil service in Nigeria were elicited with the help of graduate students who served the researcher as assistants. The choice of using State employees is because the sample has similar characteristics with those of the main study – Federal civil servants in Nigeria. The researchers visited the Federal secretariat during the official break time (1-2 pm) and gave the questionnaire to participants who are willing to be part of the study. The questionnaire was prepared in a booklet and was hand-distributed to the participants. The participants were given both oral and written instruction on how they may fill in the items in the questionnaire. The participants were assured of the confidentiality of their responses as there is no right or wrong answers, since the inquiry is only for an academic purpose.

After filling their responses to the item questions which took each of the respondents about 19 minutes, the researcher collected back the filled questionnaire from the respondents. Fifty-seven (57) questionnaire booklets were distributed but only fifty-two (52) were collected back while 50 was valid. After collecting the filled questionnaire, they were sorted and only the valid ones were coded in excel spread sheet for analysis. Cronbach's alpha reliability analysis was carried out and after analyzing the data obtained, the success of pilot study encouraged the researcher to move on to the main study.

3.6.2 Main Study

Having ensured the validity and reliability of the instruments during the pilot study, the researchers advanced to the main study with the aid of the instruments as statistical tools. The participants of the main study were employees of from Federal service at Federal secretariat Awka, Anambra State Nigeria. The researchers used simple random sampling (ballot technique) to pick ministries, departments and agencies (MDAs). The researchers after selecting ministries, departments and agencies approached those in charge in those ministries, departments and agencies for permission to carry out the study with their staff. For choosing the participants from each of the chosen ministry, department or agency, simple randomization was applied. The researchers visited the Secretariat for four working days for data collection.

During the visitations, responses of two hundred and twenty nine (229) participants were elicited for this study. The participants were made up of one hundred and sixty (160) females and sixty-nine (69) males. The respondents were informed that the research is for academic purpose as there are no right and wrong answers. On the whole, a total of 350 questionnaires were administered while 337 were collected back (96.28% return rate). Only 329 (97.6%) questionnaires were correctly filled and were used for analysis in the study. In addition to the items, demographic variables such as gender, age, marital status, educational background were included in the instrument in

order to obtain the characteristics of the population. All the raw data obtained from the field exercise were transferred to SPSS statistical tool for analyses.

3.7 Design and Statistics

Being a cross-sectional survey studies, correlation design and multiple regression analysis were used as the appropriate design and statistical tool to analyze the data obtained from the field study respectively. All statistical analyses were done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences SPSS version 16.00.

4. Results

Table 1: Shows descriptive statistics, mean, standard deviations and number of participants for the variables of the study

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Cyber-loafing	91.318	.3502	329
Abusive supervision	57.162	.4850	329
Organizational cynicism	62.6048	.3723	329

Table 2: Summary table of multiple regression analysis for predictive effects of abusive supervision and organizational cynicism on cyber-loafing

Coefficients (a)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.028	1.322	.953	1.00	.000
	Abusive supervision	.594	1.793	.512	.653	.013
	Organizational cynicism	.640	2.301	.634	.774	.002

a. Dependent Variable: Cyber-loafing

5. Summary of Findings

The result from the multiple regression table above (table 2) confirmed that hypothesis I which stated that abusive supervision will significantly predict cyber-loafing among civil servants was confirmed at $\alpha = .51$, $p < .05$ ($n=229$) and hypothesis II which stated that organizational cynicism significantly predict cyber-loafing among civil servants was also confirmed at $\alpha = .63$, $p < .05$ ($n=229$). From the findings above, the regression result produced positive relationship negative implying that the predictor variables (abusive supervision and organizational cynicism are in directional relationship with the dependent variable (cyber-loafing). This means that as abusive supervision and organizational cynicism increases, cyber-loafing increases also.

6. Discussion

This study investigated abusive supervision and organizational cynicism as predictors of cyber-loafing among federal civil servants in Anambra State. Two hypotheses were tested after the analysis of the data obtained from the field work. The result confirmed that both abusive supervision and organizational cynicism significantly predicted cyber-loafing among civil servants. The tested relationship of the study was found in positive direction indicating that with more abuse of the employees by their supervisors and growing cynical behaviour of the employees, there is higher incidence of cyber-loafing among employees to the disadvantage of the organization.

Hypothesis I which stated that abusive supervision will significantly predict cyber-loafing among civil servants was confirmed. The statistical confirmation showed a positive and significant predictive effect exists between the predictor and dependent variable; an indication that as abusive supervision increases, cyber-loafing increases also. The finding is supported by Mark's (2008) role stressors theory which proposed a triadic model and response of the body to any demand made in an organization and this kind of demand which comes in form of negative demand may wearied down on the coping capacity of the employees a situation capable of insinuating varying deviant behaviour including cyber-loafing. The finding in hypothesis I is supported by Hamid, Juhdi, Ismail and Abdullah's (2016) study which investigated the influence of abusive supervision on workplace deviance as moderated by spiritual intelligence: an empirical study of Selangor employees. Empirical evidence of their study suggested that subordinates respond quite negatively to supervisor's mistreatment by engaging in behaviours that are harmful to the organization and its members and one of these harmful behaviours could be cyber-loafing at a high cost to the organization.

Further support was found in Liberman, Seidman, McKenna, and Buffardi's (2011) study which confirmed that certain employee job attitudes, organizational characteristics increases attitudes towards cyber-loafing and other non-Internet loafing behaviors which serve as antecedents to cyber-loafing behaviors. There are other studies which has supported this for instance; the nature of role stressors among business executives in Lars' (2001) research have been found to impact certain business organizational practices due to the effects of role stressors such that can be caused by abusive supervision of subordinates.

Also, Wang, Mao, Wu, & Liu's (2012) study on abusive supervision and workplace deviance: found that the mediating role of interactional justice and the moderating role of power distance influenced deviant behavior as among employees. The power distance problem can be observed in terms of abusive supervision. Their study replicates previous studies by examining the effects of abusive supervision on employee deviant behaviours in the Chinese organizational context which has shown considerable similarity in the Nigeria setting.

Kelloway (2010) equally ascertained that if role stressors reach an intensified level among individuals, this will reduce job satisfaction and organizational

commitment giving room for varying counterproductive workplace behaviour such as cyber-loading; which has direct and indirect cost of role stressors and this is measured in both humanistic and financial terms. The humanistic perspective identifies the relationship between role stressors (supervisors) and the impact on the individual (subordinates).

The relationship between abusive supervision and cyber-loading as a form deviant behaviour may be understood using Retaliation theory by Nathan, William and Mary (2010) which proposes and argues that deterrence theory is logically established to curb on retaliation as it involves negative internal and external characteristics of individual(s). Retaliation theory considers harmful acts conducted in response to feelings of having been wrongly treated, but in this case, the focus is specifically on injustice. For instance, Smollan (2012) noted how anger and outrage are emotions experienced in response to injustice and these can precede counterproductive workplace behaviours this pattern also explains predictive effects of abusive supervision and cyber-loading.

Hypothesis II which stated that organizational cynicism will significantly predict cyber-loading among civil servants was also confirmed. From the findings above, the regression result produced positive relationship negative implying that the predictor variable (organizational cynicism) is in directional relationship with the dependent variable (cyber-loading). This means that as organizational cynicism increases, cyber-loading increases also.

The above finding is supported by motivational approach of Kanugo (1979, 1982) which integrates the different approaches to job involvement, including both psychological and sociological factors, using the basic concept that job involvement is affected by the potential for personal socialization experience and the likelihood that the work environment satisfies personal demand. From Kanugo (1979, 1982) model it can be harnessed that personal socialization experience between the subordinate and the supervisor may become antecedent for de-motivation and less involvement in organization which is capable of breeding passivity such as: cyber-loading.

Shahzad and Mahmood's (2012) study which investigated the mediating-moderating model of organizational cynicism on employee outcome about the staff, organization and workplace deviant behaviour of bank employees including branch managers and operatives of domestic private banks in Rawalpindi/Islamabad, Pakistan also provided empirical evidence for understanding the relationship between organizational cynicism and varying deviant behaviours. The result from the survey showed that there is a significant positive association among entrepreneurial intention as employee job outcome, organizational cynicism as workplace deviant behaviour, commitment behaviour and performance.

Ogunbamila's (2013) study which investigated the extent to which perceptions of organizational politics, cynicism, and employee job-related outcomes predicted negative emotions in the workplace. The finding insisted that negative job related emotions are the antecedents of counterproductive or deviant behaviours in the

workplace. These job-related negative emotions significantly predicted workplace incivility in such a way that employees who felt bad about their jobs tended to exhibit workplace incivility. Unauthorized use of organizational internet (cyber-loafing) for personal purposes is a form of employee incivility.

7. Implications of the Study

From the findings, the role of leader-member exchange as critical determinant of workplace deviance is implicated. The relationship between supervisors and their subordinates could facilitate both palatable and unpalatable outcomes in the organization; one of the unpalatable outcomes being cyber-loafing. One of the dangers of abuse is that it culminates in retaliation. In the workplace, retaliation following abuse may take various forms especially if the employee still wants to keep the job. One form of workplace retaliation is by being unproductive which can be disguised in form of cyber-loafing. From literature, there is a high correlation following retaliatory theory between abuse and deviance in the workplace. The situation can be worrisome because it reduces productivity and efficiency. Also, the findings of the current study implicated cynical behaviours in the organization as the antecedents ushering in large scale deviance behaviour in the workplace. Loss of trust in the organizational goals and focus could be negative antecedents predicting organizational counterproductive workplace behaviour and deviant behaviours. These may take the form of cyber-loafing.

7.1 Limitation of the Study

No work is without limitations; a number of factors may limit the generalizability of the findings. Such factors are:

The current study did not take into consideration factors such as socioeconomic variables and cultural barriers which may have their own influences in the use of internet in the organization for personal reasons. Employees who have their own personal computers and internet services may not find it attractive in the workplaces as a deviant path.

The finding is also limited because of the problem of respondents' bias to the items meant to elicit the respondents' behaviour. This may stem from the need to comply with social expectation or for the fear of being sacked or punished by the organization or superiors.

7.2 Recommendations

Sequel to the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made;

It is recommended that, the organization spell out the rules of engagement regarding the use of organizational properties and facilities in order to maintain order and sanity among the organizational members. It is also recommended that workers be allowed some fringe benefits in the workplace to enable them feel appreciated and respected in the workplace with reduced temptation to use unapproved or

unauthorized usages. It also recommended also that the organizational hierarchy promote effective leader-member exchange and healthy social interaction in the workplace and how to minimize the excesses of the management in order to reduce the incidence of supervisors' abuse

7.3 Suggestion for Further Study

The model of the study only correlated the variables the dependent variable with the independent variables. There is need for a new model to find out if the relationship between the independent variables the dependent variable can be mediated in the presence of a third variable. Consequently, it is recommended the design should also focus on the possibility that the interaction effects among other organizational antecedents may likely influence the result of other variables.

8. Conclusion

This study examined the abusive supervision and organizational cynicism as predictor of cyber-loafing among federal civil service employees. What was sought was the predictive effect of abusive supervision and organizational cynicism on cyber-loafing. After extensive review of literature on the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable correlation design was adopted for the study while multiple regression analysis was used as appropriate statistical tool for analyzing the result in two tested hypotheses. The result confirmed that abusive supervision and organizational cynicism both predicted cyber-loafing behaviour.

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Appendix I

Questionnaire

Part One: Personal Information

1. Gender: Male () Female ()
2. Age:
3. Marital Status:
4. Highest Educational Qualification
5. How long have you been in your present organization?
6. Employment status.....
7. Permanent staff () Contract staff ()
8. Job position: Senior staff () Junior staff ()

Part Two: Questionnaire

Instruction: The following are questions you are very familiar with; respond in affirmation to 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Undecided, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree or as will be indicated. There is no right or wrong answers, leave no question unanswered; your responses is strictly for academic inquiry and will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

Cyberloafing Questionnaire

By Li and Chung (2006)

Cyberloafing activities = 1-12; Cyberloafing behaviours = 13-24

I engage in Cyberloafing in order to...

(Almost) Never Incidentally Occasionally Regularly (Almost) Always

1. ...maintain social network (Social 1)
2. ...find news (Informational 1)
3. ...listen to (and possibly save) music (Leisure 1)
4. ...shop online (Virtual emotional 1)
5. ...search for social support (Social 2)
6. ...express opinion (Informational 2)
7. ...save a game (Leisure 2)
8. ...play gambling game (e.g. poker or roulette) (Virtual emotional 2)
9. ... Extend social network (Social 3)
10. ... Search information (Informational 3)
11. ...play an online game (Leisure 3)
12. ...date online (Virtual emotional 3)
13. ...recover from work (Recovery 1)
14. ...avoid work tasks (Deviant 1)
15. ...learn new skills (Development 1)
16. ...follow developments on sites (Addiction 1)
17. ...take a rest (Recovery 2)
18. ...avoid thinking of work tasks (Deviant 2)
19. ...development myself (Development 2)
20. ...visit one or multiple sites daily (Addiction 2)
21. ...relax (Recovery 3)

22. ...postpone work tasks (Deviant 3)
23. ...acquire abilities (Development 3)
24. ...visit one or multiple sites out of habit (Addiction 3)

Abusive Supervision Scale

Items

1. My boss ridicules me.
2. My boss tells me my thoughts or feelings are stupid.
3. My boss gives me the silent treatment.
4. My boss puts me down in front of others.
5. My boss invades my privacy.
6. My boss reminds me of my past mistakes and failures.
7. My boss doesn't give me credit for jobs requiring a lot of effort.
8. My boss blames me to save himself/herself embarrassment.
9. My boss breaks promises he/she makes.
10. My boss expresses anger at me when he/she is mad for another reason.
11. My boss makes negative comments about me to others.
12. My boss is rude to me.
13. My boss does not allow me to interact with my coworkers.
14. My boss tells me I'm incompetent.
15. My boss lies to me.

Organizational Cynicism

1. ___ I believe my organization district says one thing and does another.
2. ___ My organization district's policies, goals, and practices seem to have little in common.
3. ___ When my organization district says it's going to do something, I wonder if it will really happen.
4. ___ My organization district expects one thing of its employees, but rewards another.
5. ___ I see little similarity between what my organization district says it will do and what it actually does.
6. ___ I often experience irritation when I think about my organization district.
7. ___ I often experience aggravation when I think about my organization district.
8. ___ I often experience tension when I think about my organization district.
9. ___ I often experience anxiety when I think about my organization district.
10. ___ I complain about how things happen in my school district to friends outside the organization.
11. ___ I exchange "knowing" glances with my coworkers.
12. ___ I often talk to others about the ways things are run in my organization district.
13. ___ I criticize my school district's practices and policies with others.
14. ___ I find myself mocking my organization district's slogans and initiatives.

Appendix II

Statistical Analysis

Multiple Regressions Analysis

Descriptive statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Cyber-loading	91.318	.3502	329
Abusive supervision	57.162	.4850	329
Organizational cynicism	62.6048	.3723	329

Coefficients (a)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.028	1.322	.953	1.00	.000
	Abusive supervision	.594	1.793	.512	.653	.013
	Organizational cynicism	.640	2.301	.634	.774	.002

a Dependent Variable: Cyber-loading

Variables Entered/Removed (b)

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Abusive supervision (a) Organizational cynicism	.	Enter

a All requested variables entered.

b Dependent Variable: Cyber-loading

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	Sig. F Change	R Square Change	F Change
1	.632(a)	.583	.565	3.73906	.563	230.140	2	329	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Abusive Supervision, Organizational cynicism

b. Cyber-loading

Model Summary

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	134.226	2	67.113	73.727	.000(a)
	Residual	248.509	327	.910		
	Total	382.736	329			

a Predictors: (Constant), Abusive supervision, Organizational cynicism

b Dependent Variable: Cyber-loading

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